

Evaluating integrated nutrient management for the *biasi* system of rainfed rice cultivation

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Biasi is a set of cultural operations traditionally practiced in direct-seeded rice. In this operation, the field is plowed by an indigenous plow in standing water 30–50 d after emergence. Bullock plowing often followed planking and *chalai* (thinning and distribution) operations. This system is very popular in the eastern region of India; about 75% of the area (25.5 million ha) is under the *biasi* system. The effectiveness of the system greatly affects yield. Often, operation is delayed because there is less rain to flood the field. The post-*biasi* operation, which is done to redistribute seedlings, has high labor requirements and is costly. The other major drawbacks are high plant mortality (38–40%) and heavy weed intensity. It is important to evaluate a suitable integrated nutrient management system under *biasi* to increase yield with minimal operational cost. Use of green manure, especially *Sesbania rostrata*, which nodulates in roots as well as in stems, gives better performance and maintains the nutrient supply. A significant savings of 40 kg N ha⁻¹ was recorded by incorporating 40-d-old *S. rostrata* in a standing rice crop under *biasi* (IGKV 1994).

Green manure incorporation will thus improve yield.

A field experiment was conducted in a farmer's field near IGAU during the 2000-01 kharif under rainfed conditions. It was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. The treatments consisted of no fertilizer, with inorganic fertilizer, and a combination of inorganic plus biofertilizer—0-0-0 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (T₁), 60-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (T₂), and 30-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + *S. rostrata* + phosphorus-soluble bacteria (PSB) (T₃). Rice variety IR36 (at a seeding rate of 100 kg ha⁻¹) and *S. rostrata* (at 10 kg ha⁻¹) were mixed and then broadcast. Initially, powdered PSB at 5 g kg⁻¹ of seed was thoroughly mixed

with the rice seed. *Biasi* was done at 40 d after sowing (DAS), followed by *chalai*. At the same time, *S. rostrata* was buried in the soil and allowed to decompose. Other pre- and postharvest observations were made and analyzed. The pooled data are presented in Tables 1–3.

No treatment had a significant effect on the plant population before *biasi* (Table 1). Treatment T₃ gave the lowest plant mortality (22.0%) due to *biasi*, followed by treatment T₂ (24.82%). A non-significant effect on weeding efficiency was found because of *biasi*. However, the highest weeding efficiency was noted under T₃. This may be because fewer weeds appeared in the rice crop

Table 1. Effect of various nutrient management treatments on growth and population of rice under the *biasi* system.

Treatment	Plant population (before <i>biasi</i>) (no. m ⁻²)	Plant population (after <i>biasi</i>) (no. m ⁻²)	Plant loss due to <i>biasi</i> (%)	Plant height (cm)	No. of weeds per m ² (before <i>biasi</i>)	No. of weeds per m ² (after <i>biasi</i>)	Weeding efficiency (%)
0-0-0 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	251	180	28	62.2	319	145	63
60-30-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	286	215	25	64.7	405	149	63
30-30-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	277	216	22	65.4	377	136	63
+ GM + PSB	ns	ns	3.55	1.22	ns	ns	ns
CD (0.05)							

Table 2. Effect of various nutrient management treatments on yield and yield attributes of rice under the *biasi* system.

Treatment	Panicles (no. m ⁻²)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains per panicle (no.)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)
0-0-0 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	252	17.58	62.3	25.45	1.9	2.7
60-30-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	381	18.13	74.5	26.60	2.8	4.1
30-30-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	398	18.75	81.8	27.18	3.0	4.3
+ GM + PSB						
CD (0.05)	3.86	0.39	6.38	1.26	2.53	1.66

before the *biasi* operation as most weeds were suppressed by the *S. rostrata*; in T₂, no green manure was used.

Application of 30-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + *S. rostrata* + PSB resulted in significantly high plant height (65.4 cm), panicle length (18.75 cm), number of grains panicle⁻¹ (82), and 1,000-grain weight (27.18 g) (Tables 1 and 2). These observations confirmed the findings of Hiremath and Patel (1998), who reported that N application (25–100 kg ha⁻¹) along with green manure increased the values of growth and development parameters. Maximum grain yield (30.12 kg ha⁻¹) was also noted in the same treatment. Bhandari et al (1992) reported that green manure + 50% NPK produced as much rice grain yield as did 100% NPK.

Table 3 shows the economic analysis of the different integrated nutrient management packages under the *biasi* system. A net

income of Rs 7,560 ha⁻¹ was obtained with T₃ because of less chemical fertilizer applied.

Treatment 3 gave better benefits from the investment point of view; this was supported by Jeyabal et al (1999), who reported the highest (2.80–3.25) benefit-cost ratio with combined application of inorganic fertilizer and biofertilizer compared with fertilizer alone.

Application of 30-30-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + *S. rostrata* at 10 kg ha⁻¹ + PSB gave higher grain yield and net income than did the rest of the nutrient management packages. This treatment may be recommended under the traditional *biasi* system to improve rainfed rice cultivation.

Table 3. Economic analysis of various nutrient management treatments under the *biasi* system.

Treatment	Cost of cultivation (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Gross income (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Net income (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Benefit-cost ratio
0-0-0 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	7,140	9,897	2,757	0.36
60-30-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹	8,592	15,015	6,423	0.75
30-30-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + GM + PSB	8,440	16,020	7,560	0.90

References

- Bhandari AL, Sood A, Sharma KM, Rana DS, Sood A. 1992. Integrated nutrient management in rice wheat system. *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.* 40(4):742-747.
- Hiremath SM, Patel ZG. 1998. Effect of winter green manuring and nitrogen application on summer rice (*Oryza sativa*). *Indian J. Agron.* 43(1):71-76.
- IGKV (Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya). 1994. Rice research in Chattisgarh. Raipur: Directorate of Research, IGKV. 120 p.
- Jeyabal A, Palaniappan SP, Chelliah S. 1999. Evaluation of integrated nutrient management techniques in rice. *Oryza* 36(3):363-365.

Chemical properties of lateritic soil and yield of rice as influenced by addition of fly ash

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Fly ash is a waste product from thermal power stations. It has no economic use and it is a pollution hazard. Coir pith is an organic waste and rice husk ash is a rare waste product from rice mills. A study was undertaken to assess the use of these waste materials in improving the lateritic soils of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India, under irrigated rice cultivation. In this area, rainfall

is more than 1,500 mm. Because of slow soil reaction during rice cultivation, most of the macro- and micronutrients are not in the available form, resulting in low productivity. A field experiment was conducted in a farmer's field. The lateritic soil has a pH of 4.79. Rice variety ADT37 was used. Different combinations of fly ash (10 and 15 t ha⁻¹) with different doses of lime, rice husk ash

(12.5 t ha⁻¹), raw coir pith (12.5 t ha⁻¹), and coir pith compost (12.5 t ha⁻¹) were tried in a randomized block design with three replications. Initial and postharvest soil samples were collected and their chemical properties analyzed (Jackson 1973). Grain and straw yields were also recorded.

Fly ash is a potentially problematic waste product after the combustion of coal in thermal